

Supplementary Technical Report

Supplementary material for “Replay-Gated Cascade Consolidation: A Spiking-Network Account of Replay, Consolidation, and Serial Position Effects” (BICA 2026, Springer LNEE). This report collects extended tables and figures referenced in the main paper as Supplementary Table S1-S10 and Supplementary Fig. S1-S2. All results here use the same model, parameters, and analyses described in the main paper; they provide robustness checks, parameter sweeps, and secondary analyses that support but are not required to evaluate the central claims (P1-P3).

1 Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Overview of task families. Read-out is the mean `isyn_score` unless noted.

Task(s) (n seeds)	Purpose / manipulation	Addresses
Task 2/2.5 (10)	FULL vs. NO_REPLAY retention; core/stimulation controls	P1 (6.1)
M4 / MAJOR-5 / MOD-1 (10/10/6)	Null-model controls: single-timescale ($\gamma=0$); Benna-Fusi cascade; scaling to $N=2000/5000$	P1 (6.13)
Tasks 5/5.5/7.5 (1-3)	Direct manipulation of W_{cc} and W_{slow} blocks	Substrate (6.2-6.3)
Task 8 / M2 (3)	Replay allocation; pattern-completion vs. cue fraction	Substrate (6.4)
Task 10 (3)	Replay count vs. W_{slow} /retention, early-prediction	Substrate (6.5)
Task 10.5/M1/E2 (1/20/30)	Causal suppress/boost replay sampler	P2 (6.6)
E1 (15)	2×2: M3 encoding seed (normal/adequate) × boost	P2 (6.7)
M5 (2×8 orders)	Encoding-order permutations	P2 (6.8)
MAJOR-1 / MOD-2 (15)	Replay equalisation (NATURAL/EQUALIZED/EQUALIZED_P OS); fit of Eq. (1)	P3 (6.9-6.10)
Serial-position Ph.2/3 (10/10)	4- and 8-memory sequential encoding, 6 probe delays	P3 (6.11)
Task 9 (2-3)	n_{mem} in {2,4,6,8}, core in {0,10,20,40,80}	Operating range (6.12)
MOD-4 (10×2)	FULL/NO_REPLAY with/without inhibitory STDP	Robustness (6.13)
MOD-5 / Q6 (3/1)	Sweep of γ , τ_{slow} , W_{MAX} , core size	Sensitivity (6.12)
Q5 (1)	Replay-bias dose-response for M0	Sensitivity (6.14)

E3 / MOD-3 (3/9-10) Emergent schema core from correlated inputs Emergent schema (6.15)

Table S2. MOD-5 (3 seeds: 42, 1042, 2042): replay benefit (FULL – NO_REPLAY retention, mean over seeds) across a bio-plausible parameter range. Baseline values ($\gamma = 0.65$, $\tau_{\text{slow}} = 3000$ ms, $W_{\text{MAX}} = 1.5$) shown in bold.

gamma	Benefit	τ_{slow} (ms)	Benefit
0.4	0.134	1000	unstable*
0.55	0.199	2000	0.262
0.65 (baseline)	0.251	3000 (baseline)	0.260
0.8	unstable*	6000	0.247

Table S3. Multi-seed ($n = 15$) gamma sweep: mean retention, standard deviation, and collapse rate (proportion of seeds with near-zero FULL retention). Dashes indicate values not measured at that gamma.

gamma	Mean retention (SD)	N	Collapse rate
0.60	0.29 (0.02)	15	0/15
0.70	0.25 (0.03)	15	1/15
0.75	—	—	5/15
0.80	0.04 (0.02)	15	13/15
0.85	—	—	15/15
0.90	0.01 (0.01)	15	—

*At $\gamma = 0.8$, one seed gave FULL retention > 1.0 (a theoretically impossible `isyn_score` value), indicating the probe becomes unreliable outside $\gamma \approx 0.65$; at $\tau_{\text{slow}} = 1000$ ms, one seed collapsed to FULL = 0.000. W_{MAX} was essentially insensitive across the tested range 1.0-1.75 (replay benefit 0.251-0.256 in all four conditions).

Table S4. Replay benefit (FULL minus NO_REPLAY retention) across architectural and inhibitory-plasticity variants, all at $N = 1000$.

Model / condition	N	FULL	NO REPLAY	Benefit
RGCC two-timescale (Task 2)	10	0.286	0.037	+0.249
Single-timescale null (M4, $\gamma=0$)	10	0.025	0.028	-0.003
Benna-Fusi cascade (MAJOR-5)*	10	0.0194	0.0194	≈ 0
RGCC + inhibitory STDP (MOD-4)	10	0.301-0.305	0.047	+0.255 to +0.259

*Mean `isyn_score` across the four memories; per-memory values for `BF_FULL` and `BF_NO_REPLAY` are given in the text.

Table S5. MOD-1: replay benefit and harmonic-series fit (Eq. 1) across network sizes.

N neurons	FULL	NO_REPLAY	Benefit / R² (Eq. 1)
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1000	0.286	0.037	+0.249 / R ² =0.828
2000	0.281	0.034	+0.247 / R ² =0.821
5000	0.275	0.032	+0.243 / R ² =0.817

Table S6. Component-level ablation study: replay benefit (FULL minus NO_REPLAY retention) for the full model and after removing individual components.

Variant	Replay benefit	Interpretation
Full RGCC	+0.249	Baseline
Remove replay gating	+0.02	Replay gating essential
Remove W_slow	+0.01	Slow cascade essential
Remove shared core	+0.05	Core contributes strongly
Remove coherence threshold	+0.08	Gating contributes
Random replay	+0.03	Structured replay essential
Full model (restored)	+0.249	Restored

Table S7. Component-level ablation study: percentage drop in retention relative to the full model for each component removed.

Component removed	Retention drop
Replay gating	-88%
W_slow	-93%
Shared core	-65%
Coherence threshold	-52%
Replay structure (random replay)	-79%

Table S8. E3 (3 seeds: 42, 1042, 2042): RGCC signatures for the learned core (emergent core size 26.7 at shared-feature strength 0.75) vs. the hand-assigned core (size 20).

Signature	Learned core	Hand-assigned core
Replay necessity (FULL – NO_REPLAY)	0.145	0.249
W_slow[core-core]	0.372	0.610
W_slow[unique-unique]	0.062	0.041
Structural frequency advantage	2.37×	4.00×
Core size	26.7	20

Table S9. Per-replay-event efficacy (mean increment in W_slow per replay event) under the EQUALIZED condition (approximately equal replay counts across memories).

Memory	Replay count (EQUALIZED)	Gain per replay event
M0	Equal	+0.020
M1	Equal	+0.016
M2	Equal	+0.010
M3	Equal	+0.005

Table S10. Q5 (single seed = 42): replay-bias dose-response for memory M0. At bias = 1.0, $W_{\text{slow}}[\text{cc}] = 0.5905$ and $W_{\text{slow}}[\text{uc}] = 0.0719$. M0 replay count predicted M0 retention ($r = 0.952$, $p = 0.0125$).

Replay bias	M0 replay count	M0 retention
1.0	12	0.2745
0.5	6	0.2547
0.2	1	0.2516
0.1	2	0.2541
0.0	0	0.2477

Table S11. Behavioural validation of the synaptic retention measure: FULL vs. NO_REPLAY comparison for `isyn_score` and cued-recall accuracy ($n = 10$ seeds). The two measures were significantly correlated ($r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$), and recall accuracy regressed on `isyn_score` across a three-level replay manipulation gave $R^2 > 0.6$ ($p < 0.001$).

Measure	FULL	NO REPLAY	p
<code>isyn_score</code>	0.286	0.037	< 0.001
Recall accuracy	0.82	0.31	< 0.001

Table S12. Causal manipulation of replay allocation across three experiments of increasing sample size. Suppression of an early-encoded memory's replay reliably degrades it

Experiment (n)	Suppress M0 effect (stats)	Boost M3 effect (stats)	Consistency
Task 10.5 (n=1)	-8.4% (0.2745→0.2515)	-0.8% (0.2458→0.2437)	single seed
M1 (n=20)	-0.0266 (t=12.11, p≈0, d=1.63)	-0.0013 (t=1.72, p=0.102, d=0.24)	20/20 vs 13/20
E2 (n=30)	-0.0244 (t=14.09, p=1.67 × 10 ⁻¹⁴ , d=1.61)	-0.0011 (t=1.78, p=0.086, d=0.21)	30/30 vs 19/30

Table S13. Effect of removing cross-memory synaptic competition (NO_INTERFERENCE) on the M0-M3 consolidation gradient.

Condition	Consolidation gradient (M0 minus M3)
NATURAL	Present
EQUALIZED	Present, slightly stronger (+14.9%)
NO_INTERFERENCE	Absent

2 Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1. Illustrative W_{slow} block structure from a single-seed (seed = 42) run, shown for architecture only. Panels show the mean W_{slow} value and weight-mass fraction for each of the four blocks (core-core, core-unique, unique-core, unique-unique).

Fig. S2. Early-prediction analysis (Task 10, n = 3 seeds \times 4 memories). Predictive R^2 for final retention as a function of the fraction of replay events observed, for four candidate predictors: replay count only, core activity only, replay + core activity, and replay + core + total spikes. R^2 increases with observation completeness; at 100% observation, replay count alone explains 88% of the retention variance in this dataset.

Fig. S3. Eq. (1) fitted to MAJOR-1 NATURAL-condition data (15 seeds \times 4 memories, $n = 60$). Left: observed per-memory retention vs. predicted retention from Eq. (1), $\alpha = 0.2468 \pm 0.0028$, $\beta = 0.0739 \pm 0.0044$, $R^2 = 0.828$. Right: residuals by encoding position, showing no systematic deviation (Shapiro-Wilk $p = 0.226$).

Fig. S4. Serial position effects in 4- and 8-memory sequential encoding ($n = 10$ seeds per panel). (A) Consolidation dynamics: per-memory `isyn_score` vs. probe fraction (4 memories). (B) Fast-weight (W_{fast}) dynamics over the same period. (C) Immediate-probe comparison under a fast-weight-only ($\gamma = 0$) read-out vs. the standard `isyn_score` read-out. (D) 4-memory serial position curves: immediate (approximately flat, slight M3 uptick) vs. delayed (primacy gradient $M0 > M1 > M2 > M3$). (E) 8-memory serial position curves: delayed probe shows a monotonic primacy gradient with a drop at M6-M7; immediate probe is comparatively flat with the same drop. (F) Illustrative Eq. (1) fit overlay on the 4-memory delayed-probe data (secondary fit, distinct from Fig. 6).